

ADVANCING DIAGNOSTICS AND RADIOTHERAPY THROUGH PHOTON-COUNTING CT

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Abstract:

Introduction: Photon-counting detectors offer distinct advantages over energy-integrating detectors in terms of low imaging noise, uniform signal response, and inherent spectral capability. Inherent spectral imaging enables material-specific imaging beyond iodine quantification.

Objective: To provide an overview of the clinical implications of photon-counting CT, focusing on enhanced diagnostics and improved treatment planning in radiotherapy. To discuss both future directions and limitations in terms of technological challenges and clinical adoption.

Methods: The study outlines several prominent applications under development, including multi-contrast detection in cardiac and abdominal imaging, tissue characterization for particle radiotherapy, and clinical imaging using synchrotron radiation photon-counting CT.

Results: Advanced software enabled by photon-counting technology can significantly reduce range uncertainty in particle therapy and detect low concentrations of gadolinium contrast agent in fibrotic tissue.

Conclusion: Photon-counting CT scanners offer a promising solution to several long-standing limitations of conventional CT imaging. New metrology will be needed to assess and compare the performance of clinical photon-counting CT systems. Adoption of technology in clinical practice will depend on the quality of data compression and representation techniques for diagnostic utility.

Keywords: photon-counting CT, particle therapy, material characterization, multi-contrast

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17TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF MEDICAL PHYSICS IN THE BALTIC STATES

07-08 November 2025, Kaunas, Lithuania

Friday, November 07, 2025

8.30-9.00	Registration of participants at Kaunas University of Technology, Santaka Valley, K. Baršausko str. 59–I and II halls, Kaunas
9.00-9.10	Conference opening: KTU representative, Sören Mattsson, Lund University, Skåne University Hospital Malmö, Eeva Boman, EFOMP representative, Diana Adlienė, Kaunas University of Technology, Head of Physics Department

Session 1. Chair: *Benas Gabrielis Urbonavičius*

9.10-9.30	<u><i>Eeva Boman</i></u> . EFOMP's ROLE IN PROMOTING THE MEDICAL PHYSICS PROFESSION IN EUROPE
9.30-9.50	<u><i>Eugene Lief, Joseph Weygand, Stephanie Parker</i></u> . COLLABORATION WITH GLOBAL REPRESENTATIVES SUBCOMMITTEE OF THE AMERICAN ASSOCIATION OF PHYSICISTS IN MEDICINE FOR ASSISTING PHYSICISTS IN LOW- AND MIDDLE-INCOME COUNTRIES
9.50-10.00	<u><i>Tomasz Piotrowski, Witold Skrzyński</i></u> . MESSAGE FROM THE POLISH SOCIETY OF MEDICAL PHYSICS
10.00-10.10	<u><i>Joosep Kepler</i></u> . HIGHLIGHTS FROM THE ESTONIAN SOCIETY FOR BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING AND MEDICAL PHYSICS
10.10-10.20	<u><i>Martins Piksis</i></u> . HIGHLIGHTS FROM THE LATVIAN SOCIETY OF MEDICAL PHYSICS
10.20-10.30	<u><i>Kirill Skovorodko</i></u> . REFLECTING ON MEDICAL PHYSICS IN LITHUANIA (ACHIEVEMENTS, CHALLENGES, AND THE ROAD AHEAD)
10.30-10.45	<i>“International Medical Physicists Day” (interactive)</i>

Coffee break 10:45-11:00

Session 2. Chair: *Christian Bernhardsson*

11:00-11.15	<u><i>Birutė Gricienė, Antonio Jreije, Leonid Krynke</i></u> . RECURRENT CT IMAGING AND RADIATION PROTECTION: SETTING RECURRENT EXPOSURE REFERENCE LEVELS
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11.15-11.30	<u>Eric Pace, Carmel J Caruana, Hilde Bosmans, Kelvin Cortis, Melvin D'anastasi, Gianluca Valentino.</u> PERSONALISED CLINICAL PROTOCOL ABDOMINO-PELVIC CT OPTIMISATION: AN INVENTORY OF OBJECTIVE PATIENT SIZE, IMAGE QUALITY, AND RADIATION DOSE METRICS
11.30-11.45	<u>Inga Andriulevičiūtė, Kirill Skovorodko, Tomas Šinkūnas, Birutė Gricienė.</u> COMPARATIVE STUDY OF OCCUPATIONAL RADIATION EXPOSURE DURING COMMON FLUOROSCOPY AND ANGIOGRAPHY PROCEDURES
11.45-11.55	<u>Vilius Milašius, Feliksas Sakalauskas, Kristina Repšė, Marius Gedvilas, Nikolajus Medvedevas, Vytenis Punys.</u> ASSESSMENT OF RADIOGRAPHIC IMAGE QUALITY THROUGH MULTIPLE X-RAY SYSTEMS: PH-1 LUNGMAN PHANTOM STUDY
11.55-12.10	<u>Clarissa Attard, Eric Pace, Keith Schembri, Carmel J Caruana.</u> A VERSION-CONTROLLED WORKFLOW FOR AUTOMATIC DIGITAL X-RAY IMAGING QC LIBRARY DESIGNED FOR EASY INTEGRATION INTO QATRACK
12.10-12.25	<u>Lucía Mariel Arana Peña, Liisa Ojaköiv, Gitana Kiudma.</u> OPTIMISING MAMMOGRAPHY IMAGE QUALITY THROUGH TARGETED TRAINING
12.25-12.35	<u>Marius Burkanas, Mindaugas Džiugelis, Jonas Venius, Romualdas Griškevičius.</u> REFINING LOW-DOSE CT PROTOCOLS USING SIMULATED IMAGE QUALITY EVALUATION
12.35-12.50	<u>Olga Posrednikova, Jevgenijs Proskurins, Aldis Balodis.</u> OPTIMISATION OF CT PROTOCOLS FOR PRESURGICAL PLANNING OF CRANIAL RECONSTRUCTION: REDUCING RADIATION DOSE WITHOUT COMPROMISING ACCURACY
12.50-13.00	<u>Nicolajus Medvedevas, Diana Adlienė, Feliksas Sakalauskas, Marius Gedvilas, Vilius Milašius.</u> ASSESSMENT OF DOSE TO PATIENT AFTER REPLACING AN X-RAY MACHINE IN THE X-RAY ROOM
13.00-13.15	<u>Leonid Kryнке, Dileta Valanciene, Antonio Jreije.</u> ASSESSMENT OF PATIENT DOSES IN A PILOT LOW-DOSE CT LUNG-CANCER SCREENING PROGRAM CONDUCTED AT VILNIUS UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL SANTAROS KLINIKOS
13:15-13:30	<u>Stevan Vrbaški.</u> ADVANCING DIAGNOSTICS AND RADIOTHERAPY THROUGH PHOTON-COUNTING CT
13:30-13:45	<u>Katrina Caikovska, Martins Piksis.</u> ENTRANCE SKIN DOSE ASSESSMENT METHOD IN PEDIATRIC X-RAY EXAMINATIONS USING AUTOSTICHING

Time for the lunch 13:45 – 14:45

Poster Session 14:00 – 14:45. Chair: Judita Puišo

Liudmyla Aslamova, Mykhaylo Zabolotnyy, Galina Dovbeshko, Olena Gnatyuk, Maksym Barabash, Valerii Orel. USE OF ELECTRON IRRADIATION OF SOME WATER-SOLUBLE ANTI-TUMORIAL DRUGS IS A WAY TO CHANGE THEIR PROPERTIES

Akvilė Kuncytė, Evelina Jaselske. THE RESPIRATORY MOTION MANAGEMENT IMPACTS IN LUNG STEREOTACTIC BODY RADIATION THERAPY (SBRT)

Sundus Osman Mohammed Osman, Shima Ibnedress Abdoalmajed Ibnedress, Esra Yahia Yosief, Kristina Štutienė, Jurgita Laurikaitienė. SECONDARY CANCER RISK ASSESSMENT BASED ON IRRADIATION OF ORGANS AT RISK IN HEAD AND NECK CANCER CASES

Justas Povilaitis, Viktoras Rudžianskas, Evelina Jaselske, Volkan Aydemir, Margus Kangro. EVALUATION OF LARYNGEAL MOTION IN EARLY GLOTTIC CANCER RADIOTHERAPY TREATMENT ON UNITY MR-LINAC

Hilolaknon Erkinova, Shirin Arslonova, Doniyor Musayev, Satimboy Polvonov. DOSIMETRIC IMPACT OF INTERFRACTIONAL ORGAN VARIATIONS IN CERVICAL CANCER IMRT: A CBCT-BASED REPLANNING STUDY

Reda Venskauskaitė, Laimonas Jaruševičius, Jurgita Laurikaitienė. EVALUATION OF 3D-PRINTED MATERIALS EQUIVALENT TO FUNCTIONAL BIOLOGICAL TISSUES AND THEIR APPLICATION IN CLINICAL PRACTICE

Mostafa Laoues, Ahmed Sidi Moussa. VALIDATION OF BLADDER PREPARATION PROTOCOLS IN PROSTATE TOMOTHERAPY: A DOSIMETRIC AND CLINICAL ANALYSIS

Gustė Laurikaitytė, Romualdas Griškevičius, Marius Laurikaitis. DEVELOPMENT OF RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE QUALITY CONTROL OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING IN LITHUANIAN HEALTH CARE INSTITUTIONS

Youssef Adib, Ahmed El Ghanmi, Moulay Ali Youssoufi, Lalla Btissam Drissi, Khalid Hassouni. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASE PATIENT-SPECIFIC QUALITY ASSURANCE FOR VMAT H&N TREATMENT PLANS

Soon will be announced...

Shahd Elkhider, Mohamed Ahmed Baba, Dainius Zienius, Raimundas Lelešius, Algirdas Šalomskas, Asta Tamulevičienė, Tomas Tamulevičius. AGING EFFECTS ON LASER-ABLATED COPPER NANOPARTICLES FOR ANTIMICROBIAL USE

Session 3. Chair: Martins Piksis

14.45-14.55	<u>Evelina Jaselské, Viktoras Rudžianskas.</u> PERSONALIZED ADAPTIVE STEREOTACTIC MR IMAGE-GUIDED RADIOTHERAPY – MR-LINAC EXPERIENCE IN LITHUANIA (results from LRC funded project S-MIP-66 “Precision medicine: stereotactic ablative magnetic resonance image-guided radiotherapy for early-stage laryngeal cancer (SMART))
14.55-15:05	<u>Diana Adlienė.</u> ATTENUATION PROPERTIES OF 3D PRINTED POLYMER COMPOSITES IRRADIATED IN MIXED PHOTON AND NEUTRON BEAMS (first results from LRC funded project S-CERN-24-1 Development of lead-free adaptive modular radiation protection constructions against mixed high-energy radiation in nuclear medicine (ADAM))
15:05-15:15	<u>Benas G. Urbonavičius, Andrius Tidikas.</u> MODELING GUIDED DEVELOPMENT OF 3D PRINTABLE MULTI MODAL SHIELDING COMPOSITES (results from the joint KTU-LEI “Santaka” valley project)
15.15-15.25	<u>Rūta Racz, Mindaugas Šarpis.</u> CERN LHCb ACTIVITIES IN LITHUANIA AND POSSIBLE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER TO MEDICAL PHYSICS COMMUNITY

15.25-15.35	<u>Kristaps Palskis, Erika Korobeinikova.</u> ADVANCED PARTICLE THERAPY CENTRE FOR THE BALTIC STATES”: STATUS OF THE INITIATIVE AND OUTLOOK ON FEASIBILITY STUDY
15.35-15.45	<u>Džiugas Vyšniauskas, Marina Konstantinova, Rita Plukienė, Artūras Plukis, Emilis Sadrejevas, Paulius Kazlauskas.</u> THE NEUTRON FLUX AND DOSE RATE EVALUATION INSIDE AND OUTSIDE OF THE PU-BE NEUTRON SOURCES STORAGE DEVICE AT EXPERIMENTAL NUCLEAR PHYSICS LABORATORY OF FTMC
15.45-16.00	Soon will be announced...

Coffee break 16.00-16:20

Session 4. Chair: Kirill Skovorodko

16.20-16.35	<u>Martin Andersson, Eva Forssell-Aronsson, Rich Leggett, Sören Mattsson.</u> BLOCKING STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMAL THYROID PROTECTION FOR RADIOIODINE
16.35-16:45	<u>Kristina Repse, Vilius Milasius, Aurimas Krauleidis, Vytenis Punys.</u> EVALUATION OF CT ACQUISITION PARAMETERS AND SIZE DISTORTIONS IN HYBRID SPECT/CT LUNG NODULES IMAGING USING ^{99m} Tc: A PHANTOM BASED STUDY
16:45-17.00	<u>Mantvydas Merkis, Gabija Stašytė, Agnė Lisauskaitė, Eglė Balčiūnaitė, Deivydas Giedrimas, Ieva Jogaitė.</u> TRENDS IN OCCUPATIONAL RADIATION EXPOSURE RELATED TO FACILITY-SYNTHESISED PET RADIOPHARMECEUTICALS AT A UNIVERSITY HEALTH CENTER IN KAUNAS, LITHUANIA
17.00-17.10	<u>Klāvs Kaspars, Vineta Vanaga, Laura Antra Grikke.</u> IMPACT OF Q.CLEAR RECONSTRUCTION ALGORITHM PARAMETERS ON SPECT/CT IMAGE QUALITY
17.10-17.25	<u>Kirill Skovorodko, Kristina Kristinaitytė, Ernestas Svirbutavičius, Inga Andriulevičiūtė, Renata Komiagienė.</u> IMAGE QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF THE HIGH-SENSITIVITY BGO-BASED OMNI LEGEND PET/CT SYSTEM
17.25-17.40	<u>Džiugilė Valiukevičiūtė, Nora Šlekienė, Mindaugas Džiugelis, Jonas Venius.</u> ²²³ Ra LOCALIZATION AND MICRODOSIMETRY IN CANCER CELLS
17.40-17.50	<u>Habibu Ahmad Ibrahim, Nursakinah Suardi, Abubakar Sani Garba.</u> IN VITRO ANALYSIS OF LOW-LEVEL LASER THERAPY-INDUCED STIMULATION OF NEUROBLASTOMA CELLS IN AN ALZHEIMER’S DISEASE MODEL
17:50-18:00	Soon will be announced...

19:30-22:00 Get-together party

Saturday, November 08, 2025

8.30-9.00 Registration of participants at **Kaunas University of Technology, Santaka Valley, K. Baršausko str. 59–I and II halls, Kaunas**

Session 5. Chair: Diana Adlienė

9.00-9.15	<u>Aurimas Krauleidis, Dainius Burdulis, Kristina Repšė, Romas Vilkas, Lina Gerdauskienė, Diana Adlienė.</u> RESPIRATORY MOTION-INTEGRATED DOSE VERIFICATION IN VMAT: A STUDY OF THE ARCCHECK-3DVH SYSTEM
9.15-9.25	<u>Eliina Stencele, Sandra Stepina.</u> THE IMPACT OF RAPIDPLAN™ MODEL CONFIGURATION PARAMETERS ON THE CLINICAL ACCEPTABILITY OF THE PROSTATE SIB TREATMENT PLAN
9.25-9.35	<u>Akvilė Šlėktaitė-Kišonė, Marius Burkanas, Aleksandras Cicinas, Mindaugas Džiugelis, Jonas Venius.</u> ASSESSMENT OF FLASH-INDUCED ROS SUPPRESSION ACROSS MULTIPLE DOSE AND DOSE RATE REGIMES
9.35-9.50	<u>Renata Paukštaitienė, Algimantas Kriščiukaitis, Robertas Petrolis, Reda Čerapaitė-Trušinskienė, Diana Meilutytė-Lukauskienė, Greta Karpavičienė.</u> THE IMPORTANCE OF PRECISE PATIENT POSITIONING IN IMAGE-GUIDED RADIOTHERAPY: RETROSPECTIVE EVALUATION OF ESTIMATED IRRADIATION BY REGISTERED DAILY CBCT IMAGES
9.50-10.05	<u>Martins Piksis, Janath Navod Ranaweera Kankanamalage.</u> ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DRIVEN PATIENT POSITIONING PLATFORM FOR RADIOTHERAPY TREATMENT
10.05-10.20	<u>Ramune Ulrich.</u> LAP LUNA 3D – THE NEW MORE IN SGRT
10.20-10.35	<u>Sandra Stepina.</u> REVIEW OF TWO INSTITUTION IAEA QUADRIL BASED INTERNAL CLINICAL AUDIT RESULTS
10.35-10.50	<u>Vytautas Rumbauskas, Tomas Ceponis, Eugenijus Gaubas, Arunas Kadys, Jonas Seilius, Marius Burkanas, Aleksandras Cicinas, Jonas Venius.</u> DEVELOPMENT OF WIDE-BANDGAP SEMICONDUCTOR-BASED SENSORS FOR DOSIMETRY IN FLASH THERAPY
10.50-11.05	<u>Ilze Baumgarte, Kristaps Paļskis, Maurizio Vretenar.</u> ³ He ION USAGE IN PARTICLE RADIOGRAPHY FOR PATIENT POSITION VERIFICATION IN PARTICLE THERAPY
11.05-11.20	<u>Stephane Muraro, Mathis Badreddine.</u> ASSESSMENT OF A RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DISPLACEMENTS DETECTED BY AN SGRT SYSTEM AND INSPIRATORY VOLUME
11.20-11.35	<u>Shirin Arslonova, Loris Menegotti, Diana Adliene.</u> EVALUATION OF VMAT TECHNIQUES FOR ADVANCING TREATMENT PLANNING AND ROBUSTNESS IN PAEDIATRIC CRANIOSPINAL IRRADIATION

Coffee break 11:35 -11.50

Session 6. Chair: Guillaume Pédehontaa-Hiaa

11.50-12.05	<i>Soon will be announced...</i>
12.05-12.15	<u>Kristina Kristinaitytė</u> . A POSTDOC'S JOURNEY FROM HOSPITAL HALLS TO RESEARCH LABS: A NEW CHAPTER IN THE BROADER STORY OF MEDICAL PHYSICS
12.15-12.25	<u>Vilius Žalėnas</u>, <u>Jevgenij Garankin</u>, <u>Deividas Rūškys</u>, <u>Artūras Plukis</u> . DATA ACQUISITION SYSTEM FOR SCINTILLATION DETECTORS USING SIGNAL SHAPING AND POST-PROCESSING ALGORITHMS
12.25-12.35	<u>Kamilija Jablonskaitė</u>, <u>Ali Aldujeli</u>, <u>Ieva Čiapienė</u>, <u>Ugnė Meškauskaitė</u>, <u>Indrė Matulevičiūtė</u>, <u>Vacis Tatarūnas</u>, <u>Mantas Landauskas</u> . INVESTIGATING THE LINK BETWEEN MATHEMATICAL PROPERTIES OF THE GENETIC CODE AND EPIGENETIC REGULATION
12.35-12.45	<i>Soon will be announced...</i>
12.45-12.55	<u>Edgars Elsts</u>, <u>Marina Konuhova</u>, <u>Nina Mironova-Ulmane</u>, <u>Anatoli I. Popov</u> . THERMOLUMINESCENCE STUDY OF NEUTRON-IRRADIATED $MgAl_2O_4$ CRYSTALS DOPED WITH RARE-EARTH IONS
12.55-13.05	<u>Vladimirs Kozlovs</u>, <u>Mihails Barisevs</u>, <u>Dmitrijs Merkulovs</u>, <u>Shimons Svirskis</u> . A NOVEL DIFFERENTIAL REFRACTOMETER FOR HIGH-PRECISION ANALYSIS OF BINARY LIQUID MIXTURES
13.05-13.15	<u>Muzammal Amin</u>, <u>Chiara Pedroli</u>, <u>Enrica Caputo</u>, <u>Mariachiara Girani</u>, <u>Anna Vignati</u> . EVALUATION OF INDIVIDUAL EXPOSURE TO RF ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELDS USING WEARABLE PERSONAL DOSIMETERS

Coffee break 13:15 -13.30

Session 7. Chair: Joosep Kepler

13.30-13.15	<i>Soon will be announced...</i>
13.15-13.30	<u>Guillaume Pédehontaa-Hiaa</u>, <u>Sören Mattsson</u>, <u>Nathaly De La Rosa</u>, <u>Martin Bech</u>, <u>Robert J. W. Frost</u>, <u>Ioanna Mantouvalou</u>, <u>Paula Pongrac</u>, <u>Kristina Eriksson Stenström</u> . NEW APPROACH TO THE ANALYSIS OF THE METAL DISTRIBUTION IN ALGAE BIOINDICATORS COLLECTED NEAR NUCLEAR POWER PLANTS
13.30-13.45	<u>Aishee Ghosh</u>, <u>Robert J.W. Frost</u>, <u>Paula Pongrac</u>, <u>Guillaume Pédehontaa-Hiaa</u>, <u>Christian Bernhardsson</u>, <u>Christopher L. Rääf</u> . INVESTIGATION OF TRACE RADIONUCLIDE UPTAKE AND ACCUMULATION IN PLANTS USING HYDROPONICS: X-RAY FLUORESCENCE AND NUCLEAR MICROPROBE ANALYSIS
13.45-14.00	<u>Aliaksandr Dvornik</u>, <u>Christopher L Rääf</u>, <u>Robert Finck</u> . ENHANCED BAYESIAN TECHNIQUE FOR ORPHAN GAMMA RADIATION SOURCE LOCALIZATION

14.00-14.15	<u>Robert J.W. Frost, Guillaume Pédehontaa-Hiaa, Christian Bernhardsson, Christopher L Rääf.</u> DETERMINING THE LIMITS OF DETECTION BY GAMMA-RAY SPECTROSCOPY – FOR SOIL SAMPLES WITH COMPLEX RADIONUCLIDE INVENTORIES
14.15-14.30	<u>Christian Bernhardsson.</u> CITIZEN SCIENCE WITH AFFORDABLE HAND-HELD DETECTORS
14.30-15.00	Final remarks: prof. Sören Mattsson

**KAUNAS UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
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10-05-2025

INVITATION LETTER

Dear Dr. Stevan Vrbaški,

we are pleased to invite you to participate as an **invited speaker** at the 17th International Conference & Workshop “Medical Physics in the Baltic States 2025”, organized by Kaunas University of Technology (Lithuania), the Society of Medical Physicists (Lithuania), and Skåne University Hospital Malmö (Sweden).

We are honored to include your presentation titled "**Advancing Diagnostics and Radiotherapy Through Photon-Counting CT**" in the conference program.

The conference will take place on 6–8 November 2025 at Kaunas University of Technology, Santaka Valley, K. Baršausko str. 59 I and II halls, Kaunas, Lithuania.

More information about the conference is available at: <https://medphys.lt/medphys2025/>.

We are looking forward to seeing you at Kaunas University of Technology.

Sincerely,

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Jurgita Laurikaitienė
Conference Vice Chair
<https://medphys.lt/medphys2025/>

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Živilė Rutkūnienė
Vice-Dean for Studies
Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences
Kaunas University of Technology

